

Women’s Employment and Family Trajectories Shape Health Unequally in Later Life Across Welfare Regimes

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Abstract

This study investigates how female employment and family formation trajectories jointly intersect with welfare regimes to shape later life health outcomes. Existing studies have shown a number of associations between patterns of employment/family trajectories and health at older ages. However, it remains unclear whether the accumulation of social roles, such as employment or childbearing, translates into health benefits (i.e., role accumulation) or penalties for women (i.e., role strain). This study aims at establishing how the effects vary across welfare regimes using a machine learning-based g-computation framework. We estimate the average treatment effects (ATEs) of counterfactually following typical employment and family trajectories, identified through sequence and clustering analysis, across Scandinavian, Mediterranean, and Corporatist welfare regimes. By comparing ATEs across regimes, we capture how life-course processes interact with institutional contexts to produce heterogeneous health outcomes in women’s later life. A central finding is that health advantages and disadvantages are not inherent to specific roles or trajectories themselves, but are shaped by how these trajectories are organized and supported within their institutional context.

Overall, the results highlight that the link between life-course trajectories and health is best understood when assessed within broader institutional structures that define, enable, and constrain women’s role combinations across the life course.

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1 Introduction

We ask one main question in this study: How do female employment and family trajectories intersect with welfare regimes to produce possibly diverging health outcomes in later life? Although links between life-course trajectories and later health are well documented,^{1,2,3} the extent to which social welfare contexts moderate those effects has received less attention. The benefits and penalties associated with a given trajectory are not inherent to the trajectory itself but contingent on the institutional environment in which they are embedded. In this study, we aim to analyze this intersection between welfare regime dynamics and family/work trajectories. We specifically focus on women's lives across welfare regimes because these regimes fundamentally shape the distribution of female employment opportunities and the normative expectations of women's roles in the family domain⁴ with consequences for their later-life health. In doing so, we conceptualize welfare regimes as gendered institutional arrangements that structure how women's work and family trajectories unfold over the life course and how these trajectories translate into health outcomes.

Women's families and work trajectories are the sites where their social roles are realized in everyday life. Existing studies show that not only the number and types of roles, but also their timing, duration, and sequencing across early to mid-adulthood, have important implications for later-life health.⁵ On the one hand, studies demonstrated a positive relationship between the accumulation of social roles,⁶ such as parenthood or being employed, and better health at older ages.^{7,8} Scholars proposed that *role accumulation* allows individuals to expand their social networks, enabling greater access to social support and other resources that matter for health outcomes.^{9,10} Social responsibilities also foster a sense of identity and purpose, both of which are conducive to positive mental health outcomes.¹¹ Yet, other studies have also produced contrasting support for a theory of *role strain*,¹² where having multiple social roles yield instead declining returns to health.^{13,14} This is because engaging in multiple roles can deplete resources needed to meet daily demands, and the obligations of one role may also conflict with those of another, consequently undermining health outcomes.^{12,15} Ultimately, these mixed results likely reflect the heterogeneity of labor market and family formation conditions across different institutional settings.

Welfare regimes shape both the opportunities available to women in employment and family through their life course and the normative expectations around how they should participate in each domain.^{16,17,18} Scandinavian regimes tend to facilitate female employment by providing extensive public services and policies that help balance work and family, such as affordable childcare and generous parental leave.^{17,19} In contrast, conservative

57 and Mediterranean regimes reinforce male-breadwinner models and disproportionately
58 assign caregiving burdens to women.^{4,16,20} Critically, when welfare states fail to redress
59 these imbalances, they exacerbate the penalties associated with women’s trajectories.²¹
60 Supportive policies, on the other hand, may buffer such risks,^{1,22} though evidence remains
61 inconsistent.²³ (For further elaborations on welfare configurations in these regimes, refer
62 to Appendix C.) This perspective helps explain the mixed health effects of role accu-
63 mulation: in supportive contexts, role accumulation may enhance health by expanding
64 resources and social ties, whereas in unsupportive contexts, the same combination of roles
65 can generate role strain and erode health.

66 We contribute to this debate by demonstrating that welfare regime dynamics con-
67 siderably regulate the relationship between social role engagement and health outcomes,
68 which unfold through women’s life trajectories.

69 **2 Findings**

70 **2.1 Typical Employment and Family Trajectory Patterns across** 71 **Welfare Regimes**

72 To identify representative patterns of employment and family trajectories across welfare
73 regimes, we applied multichannel sequence and cluster analysis to life-course sequences
74 constructed for all women in our sample, based on their employment and family formation
75 statuses from ages 18 to 50. Individuals with similar trajectories are grouped into clusters,
76 with each cluster representing dominant patterns of life course sequences observed within
77 the sample. We derived an optimal 4-cluster solution, based on the dendrogram, average
78 silhouette width (ASW), and elbow plots (Appendix A, Figures A1-A3). The sequence
79 index- and state distribution plots for our 4-cluster solution are shown in Appendix A
80 Figure A4-A5. Cluster-specific descriptive statistics are outlined in Appendix A Table
81 A1.

82 Figure 1 outlines the medoid sequences extracted from each cluster, providing a rep-
83 resentative summary of the typical trajectory within each group (cluster 1: $N = 8,415$;
84 cluster 2: $N = 2,328$; cluster 3: $N = 6,820$; cluster 4: $N = 3,243$). Both medoid 1 and
85 medoid 2 capture stable full-time (FT) employment but differ in family formation pat-
86 terns: medoid 1 reflects a transition into partnership in the mid-20s, immediately followed
87 by having children within a two- to three-year window, whereas medoid 2 characterizes
88 a later transition into partnership around the early 30s with no childbearing.

89 In contrast, medoids 3 and 4 are characterized by weaker labor market attachment.
90 Where both medoids include stable transitions into unions with children, medoid 3 reflects

Figure 1: Medoid sequences for four joint employment–family trajectory clusters (ages 18–50).

Columns show clusters; rows show the **employment** and **family** medoid for the same cluster (the most representative sequence). **x-axis:** Age (years). **y-axis:** not substantive (single medoid sequence; included only for plotting). Colors indicate annual states. Medoids are labeled and used throughout the paper as: 1) *FT (full-time) with Child*; 2) *FT (full-time) without Child*; 3) *UE (unemployed) with Child*; 4) *PT (part-time) with Child*.

91 trajectories marked by persistent unemployment (UE) with brief FT work experiences in
 92 their early 20s; whereas medoid 4 represents those dominated by long-term part-time
 93 (PT) employment with initial FT work experiences until their mid-20s. Henceforth, we
 94 denote the four medoids with the following descriptors: 1) *FT with Child*; 2) *FT without*
 95 *Child*; 3) *UE with Child*; 4) *PT with Child*. Each medoid sequence serves as a treatment
 96 condition for our subsequent g-computation analyses.

97 **2.2 Effects of Employment and Family Trajectories on Health**

98 In our causal analysis, we estimate potential outcomes under interventions where individ-
 99 uals follow the employment and family trajectories specified by our four medoids above.
 100 We estimated the effects of these treatment conditions on later-life functional (limitations
 101 in activities of daily living, ADL), psychological (depression), and subjective (self-rated
 102 health) health outcomes, measured between ages 65 and 75. Conceptually, our analysis
 103 illustrates how health outcomes would change on average, if the population was coun-
 104 terfactually assigned to each of the four medoid trajectories. We outline our results in

105 Figure 2. Risk ratios (RR) were calculated as the ratio of the average predicted risk under
 106 each counterfactual scenario to the observed risk in the actual data. A lower RR thus
 107 indicates that, under the counterfactual scenario, individuals are predicted to experience
 108 better health outcomes than observed in reality, whereas a higher RR indicates worse
 109 predicted health. For absolute differences in risk, Average Treatment Effects (ATEs),
 110 which quantify the absolute change in the probability of a health outcome, are provided
 111 in Appendix D.

Figure 2: Risk ratios of health outcomes by welfare regimes.

Risk ratios (RR; 0.5–1.1) for ADL limitations, depression and poor self-rated health (SRH) at ages 65–75 under counterfactual assignment to four medoid work–family trajectories (FT with children; FT without children; PT with children; UE with children), shown separately for Mediterranean, Corporatist and Scandinavian regimes. The dashed line marks RR = 1 (no difference from the observed risk); values <1 indicate lower risk.

112 We highlight three key insights from our results, which collectively demonstrate the
 113 moderating role of the institutional context. First, life trajectories characterized by con-
 114 tinuous FT employment with a later transition into partnership in the early 30s and
 115 childlessness (medoid 2, FT w/o children) were most strongly protective for health out-
 116 comes, especially in welfare regimes with strong traditional gender roles and weaker public
 117 support systems, where families, and primarily women, are expected to provide care with
 118 little state assistance. In the Mediterranean regime, this trajectory showed the strongest
 119 reduction in risk (approximately 20-35%) across all health outcomes as reported in Fig-
 120 ure 2. Similar results were observed in the Corporatist regimes (approximately 20% risk
 121 reduction), where this trajectory consistently ranks as the second most protective, and
 122 the Scandinavian regimes (approximately 10% to 30% risk reduction).

123 Ultimately, the magnitude of the protective effect of these trajectories reflects the
 124 underlying fertility-related penalty in each regime. In Mediterranean regimes, charac-
 125 terized by strong traditional gender roles and limited support for working mothers, the

126 health penalty for motherhood is substantial. Consequently, the counterfactual scenario
127 of full-time employment *without* children shows the largest potential gain. On the con-
128 trary, Scandinavian regimes, with their extensive provisions, exhibit a relatively smaller
129 and inconsistent motherhood penalty. The results in Corporatist regimes present an
130 intermediate scenario.

131 Secondly, and most strikingly, the trajectory involving a shift from full-time to part-
132 time employment in the late 20s combined with childbearing (medoid 4, PT w children)
133 exerts starkly different effects across welfare regimes. Where this trajectory largely confers
134 null to detrimental effects on health compared to the natural trajectory of the Mediter-
135 ranean regime, it contrarily resulted in the most protective effects on health within the
136 Corporatist regime. In fact, these protective effects are consistently the strongest across
137 all health outcomes there. Similar protective effects are observed in the Scandinavian
138 regime, although not to the extent exhibited by the Corporatist welfare regime. Such
139 heterogeneity in effects suggests that welfare regime dynamics strongly regulate how
140 employment-family transitions influence health, a point we elaborate on further in the
141 Discussion section.

142 Finally, the trajectory marked by persistent lack of employment (UE) and early fam-
143 ily formation, including brief full-time employment preceding union and childbearing
144 (Medoid 3, UE w/ children), does not appear as detrimental as expected. Potential
145 health outcomes under this treatment condition remain comparable to observed health
146 levels in the Mediterranean regime and are mildly protective in the Corporatist regime
147 (approximately 10-20% risk reduction), with mixed but generally neutral effects in the
148 Scandinavian regime (approximately 10% risk reduction to 5% increase in risk). These
149 results suggest that early family formation may provide compensatory psychosocial or
150 social-support benefits that partly offset the disadvantages of weak labor-market attach-
151 ment, particularly in institutional settings where family roles are socially recognized or
152 materially supported

153 **3 Discussion**

154 This study aimed to investigate how women’s typical employment and family trajectories
155 intersect with welfare regimes to produce divergent health outcomes in later life. Using
156 a two-stage causal approach, we first discover typical life-course trajectories of women’s
157 employment and family roles and then estimate their causal effects on later-life health
158 across welfare regimes. We contribute to ongoing debates about how the accumulation
159 of social roles, such as employment or childbearing, translates into health benefits (i.e.,
160 *role accumulation*) or penalties for women (i.e., *role strain*) through life course trajecto-

161 ries. Our central finding is that health advantages and disadvantages are not inherent
 162 to specific roles or trajectories themselves, but are shaped by how these trajectories are
 163 organized and supported within their institutional context. The same configurations of
 164 women’s roles in work and family, such as combining employment and motherhood, shift-
 165 ing to part-time work, or remaining childless, yield markedly different health outcomes
 166 across welfare regimes, reflecting how institutional arrangements shape the consequences
 167 of role accumulation and strain throughout the life course. Understanding the impact of
 168 employment and family trajectories on women’s health is particularly salient in the con-
 169 text of rising female labor force participation alongside persistent expectations of female
 170 caregiving.^{24,25}

171 Drawing on these findings, we synthesize them into a conceptual framework (Figure 3)
 172 that links role theory, life-course trajectories, and welfare-regime institutions in shaping
 173 women’s health. The framework illustrates how configurations of role accumulation and
 174 strain unfold over time and how their health implications are moderated by the institu-
 175 tional context, specifically, by the social valuation and material support for women’s roles
 176 in family and work within welfare regimes. The interplay between the social valuation
 177 and material support of women’s work and family roles across the life course helps ex-
 178 plain the heterogeneous health implications of employment and family trajectories across
 179 welfare regimes observed in this study.

Figure 3: Conceptual framework linking life-course trajectories to health outcomes, moderated by institutional context.

Women’s work–family life-course trajectories are linked to later-life health outcomes, with welfare-regime institutions moderating this association through **social valuation** and **material support for women’s roles**.

180 This evidence helps resolve a long-standing puzzle in the literature. On the one
 181 hand, factors such as single parenthood, childlessness, and intermittent or weak labor-
 182 market engagement are often associated with poorer health outcomes in mid- and later

183 life,^{2,21,26} consistent with the idea that the accumulation of social roles can be protective
184 for health.⁶ On the other hand, the evidence remains mixed: other studies highlight
185 the health strain associated with role overload, particularly among women who combine
186 intensive caregiving with labor-market participation.^{12,27,28} Based on our findings, the
187 mixed results in the literature likely stem from the varying institutional contexts of the
188 populations under study, where the same combination of roles can be either protective
189 or detrimental.

190 **3.1 The Double-Edged Sword of the Family in Mediterranean** 191 **Regimes**

192 In Mediterranean regimes, the most protective trajectory for women is a decisive de-
193 parture from the traditional path: delayed family formation combined with continuous
194 full-time employment and no childbearing. This finding challenges the narrative of a
195 protective familial advantage in these regions.^{29,30} This suggests that in the absence of
196 institutional buffers and support for care, as in the Mediterranean welfare regimes,^{18,20} the
197 burden of providing familial support generates overwhelming role strain, effectively un-
198 dermining potential health benefits of strong family ties. This lends support to the theory
199 of role strain,¹⁴ and is consistent with recent evidence indicating that the adverse mental
200 health effects of childlessness are strongest in contexts with greater policy support.¹ Our
201 findings extend this logic: in strongly familialistic regimes, opting out of motherhood can
202 be the most viable strategy for preserving health, allowing women to reap the benefits
203 of stable employment while avoiding the disproportionate strain generated by gendered
204 societal expectations.

205 However, role strain theory *per se* is inadequate to account for all findings in the
206 Mediterranean regime. If we assume a straightforward interpretation of this theory, re-
207 ducing the employment load of women (i.e., part-time employment) would have resulted
208 in a healthier compromise than full-time work for mothers. Instead, we found part-time
209 employment to be the most deleterious trajectory. This is possibly because of the highly
210 restrictive social safety nets in Mediterranean regimes, where individual livelihoods are
211 strongly tied to labor participation.^{16,20} In this context, part-time work is often precar-
212 ious, poorly paid, and lacking benefits.^{31,32} In this setting, it is possible that part-time
213 work fails to provide the economic independence, social status, and empowering networks
214 of full-time work,³³ while still consuming time and energy. Consequently, it offers little
215 compensatory advantage and leads to significantly worse health outcomes. This is echoed
216 in research showing that, in countries with low levels of decommodification such as Spain
217 or Italy, women's part-time employment is often involuntary and carries a heavier wage

218 and pension penalty in comparison to full-time positions, undermining households' abil-
219 ity to reach adequate living standards.^{32,34,35,36} This logic also explains the intermediate
220 positioning of other trajectories: full-time employment with children, while demanding,
221 at least offers substantial economic resources to compensate for care burdens; whereas
222 unemployment, though economically disadvantaged, allows for a singular focus on care-
223 giving without the additional strain of precarious employment.

224 **3.2 The “Viable Compromise” in Corporatist Regimes**

225 In Corporatist regimes, a transition from full-time to part-time employment occurring
226 alongside childbearing in the late 20s emerges as the optimal “viable compromise” for
227 women’s later-life health. These regimes provide a moderate level of social provisions,
228 often linked to labor-market participation,¹⁶ making part-time work sufficiently stable
229 and rewarding. The limited support for caregiving to children or older people,³⁷ however,
230 implies a high domestic burden. In this context, part-time work successfully alleviates
231 time-based role strain without sacrificing access to labor-market-linked benefits. This
232 finding is supported by past research showing that the institutional setting of Corporatist
233 regimes cushions earnings penalties associated with part-time work and parental leaves, in
234 comparison to more liberal regimes,^{38,39,40} though such penalties were still larger compared
235 to Scandinavian countries.^{36,41}

236 This suggests the Corporatist regime creates a “viable compromise.” Part-time work
237 is sufficiently regulated and protected to offer meaningful economic and social resources,
238 unlike its precarious counterpart in the Mediterranean. Simultaneously, it presents a
239 lighter resource load in comparison to full-time employment, generating stronger health
240 gains. Earlier studies in Germany, for instance, demonstrate higher levels of depression
241 among women who returned to full-time employment after parental leave, in comparison
242 to those who returned in a part-time capacity.³⁸ Economic penalties arising from part-
243 time employment are therefore regulated and buffered against, though the extent of this
244 protection varies across welfare contexts.^{39,40}

245 Conversely, the trajectory of persistent full-time employment after childbearing arises
246 as a suboptimal compromise in the Corporatist context. Unlike in the Mediterranean,
247 full-time work is not the only path to security, but the domestic burden remains high.
248 This trajectory thus combines maximum labor market strain with the full, unmitigated
249 burden of familial care, resulting in relatively worse health outcomes, consistent with
250 observed child-related health penalties in these regimes.^{22,23}

251 **3.3 Institutional Buffering and Heterogeneity in Scandinavian** 252 **Regimes**

253 Finally, the Scandinavian regime, characterized by high levels of economic and care-
254 related provisions, presents a different picture altogether: the absence of a single, uni-
255 formly “best” trajectory on their effects on three health outcomes that we consider. Life
256 courses involving employment, whether full-time, part-time, with or without children,
257 clustered near the top with modest differences.

258 This pattern suggests that this comprehensive welfare state successfully buffers the
259 negative health effects associated with both role strain and poverty. Research shows that
260 work-life conflict and motherhood gaps in well-being are smaller in Scandinavia than in
261 other settings.^{42,23} The result is not one dominant optimal path, but a narrowing of health
262 disparities across most life-course configurations that include employment.

263 This equalizing effect reflects how extensive material support establishes a protective
264 baseline across trajectories, reducing extreme disadvantage and buffering role strain, while
265 simultaneously enabling diverse pathways to good health. When material protection is
266 universally extensive and women’s employment is socially valued, the health penalties
267 associated with specific role configurations over the life course diminish, allowing multiple
268 life-course patterns to yield similarly positive health outcomes.

269 However, recent pressures on the Scandinavian welfare regime, including retrenchment
270 of public services and increasing marketization of care producing a convergence with the
271 EU average, suggest that this group of countries may move closer to the Corporatist
272 pattern in the future.^{43,44,45} Such convergence could result in greater health stratification
273 across life-course trajectories, as the erosion of comprehensive support transforms the
274 current “multiple pathways” model into one where certain configurations yield clearer
275 health advantages. Likewise, Mediterranean countries have expanded key welfare pil-
276 lars over the past two decades, narrowing their institutional gap with other European
277 models.^{46,47} If sustained, these reforms could decrease health disparities tied to specific
278 employment-family configurations and partly reduce cross-regime differences for newer
279 cohorts.

280 **3.4 Strengths and Limitations**

281 This study presents some relevant limitations that should be considered for future re-
282 search. Firstly, the analyses are based on retrospective data, which are subject to rec-
283 ollection biases. Nonetheless, SHARE retrospective data has been proven to be highly
284 reliable in several studies.⁴⁸ Secondly, due to sample limitations or the lack of theoretical
285 clarity of welfare configurations, the analysis left Liberal and post-Soviet regimes out.

286 Third, the use of clustering and medoid sequences simplifies complex life courses into a
287 few ideal types, which may not capture the full heterogeneity of individual experiences.
288 Lastly, the analysis focuses on broad regime typologies and does not explicitly model the
289 specific policy mechanisms that drive the observed effects.

290 Despite limitations, this study has notable strengths. Methodologically, by applying
291 a machine-learning G-computation framework, we are able to estimate the causal effects
292 of entire life-course trajectories on health while accounting for time-varying confounding
293 factors such as past health histories. This is particularly relevant to address the potential
294 reverse causality between health and work-family trajectories. Additionally, the use of
295 three different health measures (depression, functional limitations, and self-rated health),
296 capturing distinct dimensions of later-life well-being, enhance the robustness of the find-
297 ings. Conceptually, the study moves past a simple role accumulation–strain debate by
298 systematically demonstrating how welfare regimes fundamentally alter the health returns
299 to work and family roles.

300 4 Conclusion

301 This study provides compelling evidence that the health consequences of women’s life
302 courses are not set but embedded in the institutional context. The same combination
303 of roles over the life course - being a worker, partner, and mother - can lead to health
304 protection or harm, depending on the welfare state context. By integrating causal in-
305 ference methods with a life course and institutional perspective, we show that later-life
306 health is not merely a product of individual choices but is fundamentally shaped by the
307 policy landscapes that make certain choices more feasible, sustainable, and rewarding
308 than others. Reducing health disparities in aging populations, therefore, requires a con-
309 certed effort to reform the institutional structures that currently make women’s health
310 contingent on the precarious negotiation of work and family demands.

311 5 Data Availability

312 The SHARE data can be obtained from the Study of Health, Ageing, and Retirement
313 in Europe homepage (<https://share-eric.eu/data/>). Detailed information on how to
314 access and utilize the dataset can be found on their official website. All code required
315 to replicate our analyses can be found on Github ([https://github.com/wesleywj/](https://github.com/wesleywj/Summer-Incubator)
316 [Summer-Incubator](https://github.com/wesleywj/Summer-Incubator)).

6 Materials and Methods

6.1 Data

This study uses data from the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), a cross-national, longitudinal survey that collects data on individuals aged 50 and older, and their spouses, in a total of 27 European countries and Israel.⁴⁹ This dataset contains detailed information on health, demographics and socioeconomic conditions of the individuals at the moment of the interview. Additionally, waves 3 and 7 include retrospective life-course data for the childhood and adulthood period. This retrospective information is used to derive the work-family trajectories and other time-varying confounders, while the childhood data is used to construct measures of pre-treatment controls, and the current data is used to compute the outcomes. This study includes participants with full information on their trajectory and outcome data, hence only individuals with valid responses in any of the outcomes for ages 65-75 are kept. Missing data in pre-treatment controls are imputed using MICE (see Appendix E for details).

A total of 14 countries are part of the final sample: 7 Corporatist (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Switzerland), 4 Mediterranean (Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain), and 3 Scandinavian (Denmark, Finland, and Sweden). Further information on the inclusion criteria and welfare characteristics of each regime and country is provided in Appendix C. The final sample includes a total of 10,349 from the Corporatist states, 6,457 from the Mediterranean, and 4,000 from the Scandinavian countries.

We consider three health outcomes that capture complementary dimensions of health: 1) *functional limitations* (Activities of Daily Living, ADL); 2) *psychological health* (Depression); and 3) *subjective health* (self-rated health, SRH). Limitations in ADLs is a composite measure based on the number of limitations in carrying out functional tasks, such as dressing, walking across a room, bathing or showering, eating, getting in or out of bed and using the toilet.⁵⁰ These limitations must last or expect to last more than three

344 months. We dichotomized this measure by coding respondents as *having limitations* (1)
345 if they reported any such limitations between ages 65 to 75, and *not having limitations*
346 (0) otherwise.

347 Depression is based on the EURO-D scale, a validated scale based on 12 items. The
348 final range of the scale goes from 0 (not depressed) to 12 (very depressed). For the di-
349 chotomization, a score of 4 or higher is categorized as “depressed,” and a score below
350 4 is considered “not depressed”.⁵¹ Lastly, SRH is reported on a five-category scale (ex-
351 cellent, very good, good, fair, poor) and dichotomized as fair/poor (1) versus good/very
352 good/excellent (0).

353 The employment trajectories are derived from the Job Episode Panel (JEP), which
354 uses retrospective data collected in waves 3 and 7 of SHARE. The dataset provides
355 annual histories of labor-market status and household composition, allowing us to build
356 person-year trajectories for ages 18 to 50. This span captures prime employment and
357 family formation years while limiting right-censoring. In fact, extending trajectories
358 beyond age 50 would systematically drop respondents who entered the survey below
359 that cutpoint, yielding uneven post-50 exposure windows and differential right-censoring.
360 Working status can have the following potential states: In education (ED), Full-time
361 Employment (FT), Part-time Employment (PT), Unemployed or out of the labor force
362 (UE). Family status can have the following potential states: Not Partnered without
363 Children, Not Partnered with Children, Partnered without Children, Partnered with
364 Children. Additionally, the retrospective waves of SHARE record information about
365 periods of relevant illnesses which was used to generate person-year health trajectories to
366 act as time-variant confounders.

367 **6.2 Analytical Strategy**

368 We adopted a two-stage methodological approach in our investigation that enables Ma-
369 chine Learning (ML) based discovery and causal analysis. First, we employed multichan-
370 nel sequence analysis to trace patterns of employment and family formation across the life

371 course. We then used a clustering algorithm to discover typical trajectories from distinct
 372 clusters, based on the similarity of their life course sequences. From each cluster, we
 373 extracted a *medoid* sequence, representing the most centrally located and representative
 374 sequence within each cluster. These medoid sequences reflect the most prototypical life
 375 course trajectories as observed in the data. This first step is run on a pooled sample of
 376 all countries to produce medoids that are comparable across contexts.

Figure 4: Visual representation of the two-stage analytical design.

Stage 1 (top): multichannel sequence clustering identifies joint employment–family trajectory clusters and their medoids (ages 18–50). **Stage 2 (bottom):** medoid trajectories define treatment conditions in ML-based g-computation to estimate counterfactual outcomes and compare effects across welfare regimes (Scandinavian, Corporatist, Mediterranean).

377 Second, we employed an ML-based G-computation approach to estimate the causal
 378 effect of typical employment and family trajectories on later-life health outcomes across
 379 different welfare regimes. This method allows us to derive causal estimates by comparing
 380 observed with counterfactual health outcomes that would have occurred under alternative
 381 trajectory (i.e., “treatment”) conditions. The moderating role of welfare regimes on health
 382 outcomes is then inferred by comparing treatment effects across different welfare regimes.

383 Figure 4 summarizes the two-stage design. Stage 1 (discovery) uses multichannel

384 sequence analysis and clustering on pooled data to extract representative medoid tra-
385 jectories. Stage 2 (causal estimation) applies ML-based g -computation to simulate each
386 medoid under each welfare regime and derive regime-specific effects (ATEs/RRs).

387 In this study, our treatment condition is represented by the medoid sequences identi-
388 fied earlier. We fitted a separate G-computation model for each welfare regime to assess
389 how treatment effects differ under distinct institutional contexts. Conceptually, this ap-
390 proach asks: how would average health outcomes differ if the population followed an
391 alternative trajectory (i.e., medoid sequences), and how would such effects vary across
392 welfare regimes (Mediterranean, Corporatist, and Scandinavian)?

393 **6.2.1 Discovery: Multichannel Sequence and Cluster Analysis**

394 Our multichannel sequence analysis captures the *joint* dynamics of employment and fam-
395 ily formation trajectories for individuals. Life course employment sequences are char-
396 acterized by transitions in and out of the labor market, whereas family formation se-
397 quences capture the transitions between co-residential unions (marriage or cohabitation)
398 and childbirth across the life course. To discover typical life course trajectories, we com-
399 puted pairwise dissimilarities between individuals, based on their combined employment
400 and family formation transitions across the observed time span. This dissimilarity reflects
401 the “cost” required to transform an individual’s life course sequence into an alternative
402 sequence. Individuals with distinctively different sequences would therefore incur a higher
403 pairwise dissimilarity score compared to those with relatively similar trajectories. In this
404 study, substitution costs were weighted based on the empirical probability of transitioning
405 between particular states, with rarer transitions incurring higher costs to better capture
406 dissimilarities in life course trajectories. Pairwise dissimilarity scores were derived with
407 optimal matching, using the *TraMineR* package in R.⁵²

408 We adopted a 2-step process in our cluster analysis. First, sequence clusters were
409 derived using a Ward hierarchical clustering algorithm. We adjudicated between the
410 numerous clustering solutions by comparing the *average silhouette widths* (ASW) of al-

411 ternative solutions. The clustering solution with the highest average silhouette width was
 412 selected as our optimal solution, because it indicates the greatest within-cluster homo-
 413 geneity and between-cluster heterogeneity.⁵³ In parallel, we validated our selected solution
 414 by comparing it against a dendrogram and an elbow plot. The optimal clustering solu-
 415 tion within the dendrogram was indicated by a substantial increase in linkage distance
 416 between clusters, with longer distances indicating greater dissimilarity across clusters.⁵⁴
 417 Correspondingly, the optimal solution in our elbow plot is marked by the point at which
 418 additional clusters yielded marginal improvements in model fit.

419 After deriving the optimal number of clusters, we re-clustered our sequences using
 420 a Partition-Around-Medoid (PAM) algorithm. Medoids were then extracted from each
 421 cluster and deployed as treatment conditions for our main analysis.

422 6.2.2 Causal Analysis: G-computation

423 To estimate the causal effects of life course trajectory patterns discovered in sequence
 424 and clustering analysis, we apply the g-formula^{55,56,57,58} to estimate expected potential
 425 outcomes under hypothetical interventions in the presence of time-varying confounding:

$$\mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}}] = \int \mathbb{E}[Y \mid \vec{A} = \vec{a}, \vec{L} = \vec{l}] dP^{\vec{a}}(\vec{l}).$$

426 In this expression, Y represents the outcome (negative health outcomes), and \vec{a} refers
 427 to a complete trajectory sequence:

$$\vec{a} = \{(e_1, f_1), (e_2, f_2), \dots, (e_T, f_T)\}$$

428 where (e_t, f_t) represents employment and family status in month t . Each \vec{a} corresponds
 429 to a medoid sequence from the cluster analysis. The term $\vec{L}^{\vec{a}}$ captures time-varying
 430 confounders (any number of years of having any disease until age 50) that would evolve
 431 under trajectory \vec{a} .

432 We estimate the Average Treatment Effect (ATE) of each trajectory type as:

$$\text{ATE} = E [Y^{\vec{a}}] - E [Y^{\vec{a}^N}]$$

433 where $Y^{\vec{a}}$ is the potential outcome under the intervention trajectory \vec{a} , and $Y^{\vec{a}^N}$ is the
434 potential outcome under the natural course. These ATEs estimate the population-level
435 impact of following each representative life course trajectories, providing direct evidence
436 for how trajectory stratification operates in practice. For example, a negative ATE indi-
437 cates that following a particular trajectory type reduces the probability of having health
438 problems compared to the natural course within the welfare state regime.

439 Figure 1 presents a directed acyclic graph (DAG) representing the hypothesized causal
440 relationships among trajectory components, time-varying confounders, and downward
441 mobility. Each node (A) reflects the joint status of work and family status, at a specific
442 time point. The DAG encodes how these components evolve over time and interact
443 with time-varying confounders (L), any number of year having any disease, and creating
444 dynamic treatment-confounder feedback.

445 This structure formalizes the theoretical logic of trajectory stratification, in which
446 life course trajectory patterns causally shape long-term outcomes.⁵⁹ Estimating the total
447 effect of entire trajectories requires a method such as g-computation, which operational-
448 izes the g-formula to simulate longitudinal interventions while accounting for recursive,
449 path-dependent processes.

450 Causal identification relies on sequential conditional ignorability, consistency, and
451 positivity (detailed discussions of all identification assumptions appear in Appendix B2).
452 Sequential conditional ignorability assumes that, at each age, conditional on observed
453 confounders and the complete history of prior employment-family states (i.e., past treat-
454 ment), there are no unmeasured confounders of subsequent trajectory selection and the
455 outcome. Given the high dimensionality of exact yearly sequences, we adopt a cluster-
456 level positivity assumption: individuals are assumed to have some chance of following

Figure 5: Directed acyclic graph (DAG) illustrating time-varying treatments, confounders, and outcome.

Note: Solid arrows denote the primary causal channels; dotted arrows denote additional dependencies. Treatment A_t affects both the time-varying covariate L_t and the outcome Y , while L_t simultaneously confounds subsequent treatment assignment and mediates the effect of prior treatment on Y . This feedback structure is why conditioning on L in a standard regression introduces collider bias, and why g-computation, which forward-simulates L under the counterfactual treatment path rather than conditioning on it, is required to recover the total effect.

457 each trajectory type, given their baseline confounders. This represents a reasonable ap-
 458 proximation, as trajectory types reflect observed patterns and capture general pathway
 459 logics rather than exact sequences (see Appendix B for a test). The empirical proba-
 460 bility of any specific 33-year sequence (between age 18 to 50) is effectively zero, making
 461 positivity untenable at the sequence level.

462 We implement g-computation using Super Learner ensemble methods,⁶⁰ which com-
 463 bine multiple machine learning algorithms based on cross-validated performance. This
 464 approach allows flexible, data-adaptive estimation without strong parametric assump-
 465 tions, making it well-suited for extended time horizons, where model misspecification
 466 bias can compound over time. Outcome models include trajectory summary variables
 467 capturing the timing, intensity, and volatility of life course trajectories in employment
 468 and family. Time-varying confounder models condition on entire prior treatment his-
 469 tory and background characteristics. Separate ensembles are used for the outcome and

470 time-varying confounders models; full algorithm specifications are provided in Appendix
471 B4-B5.

472 The analysis proceeds in five steps: (1) fit Super Learner models for time-varying
473 confounders and the outcome; (2) define interventions using medoid sequences from each
474 trajectory cluster; (3) simulate each individual following each medoid trajectory; (4)
475 generate counterfactual confounders histories and outcomes under hypothetical trajec-
476 ries, adjusting for time-varying confounding; (5) compute ATEs as differences between
477 intervention and natural course expectations, with 95% confidence intervals from 1,000
478 bootstrap resamples. [61,62,63](#)

479 This approach allows us to estimate whether different trajectory types produce dif-
480 ferential health outcomes by welfare state regime. By treating trajectories as causal
481 mechanisms rather than descriptive patterns, the analysis shows how life trajectories
482 become vehicles for health stratification.

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Appendix

Appendix A. Clustering Strategy and Robustness Checks

Focus: Sequence analysis and typology validation

Includes: Cluster solution diagnostics, dendrogram, and alternative cluster specifications.

A1. Dendrogram and Cluster Quality Indicators

Figure A1: Dendrogram of multichannel life-course trajectory clusters.

Dendrogram from Ward's hierarchical clustering of employment and family trajectories ($N = 20,806$). The y-axis shows linkage height, with larger heights indicating more dissimilar clusters.

Figure A2: Silhouette-based assessment of cluster number

Average silhouette width for Optimal Matching (OM)-based clustering solutions across $k = 2-10$. The x-axis denotes the number of clusters (k) and the y-axis the mean silhouette statistic (higher values indicate better within-cluster cohesion relative to between-cluster separation).

Figure A3: Elbow Plot for OM-Based Solutions ($k = 2-10$)

Within-cluster dissimilarity as a function of the number of clusters ($k = 2-10$) for OM-based solutions. The x-axis shows k and the y-axis shows within-cluster dissimilarity; diminishing reductions as k increases indicate where added clusters yield limited improvement.

Figure A4: Sequence Index Plot ($k=4$)

Sequence index plots ($k = 4$) shown separately by cluster for employment (top row) and family/cohabitation–child status (bottom row). Each horizontal line represents one individual trajectory over age (x-axis). Employment states are coded as full-time (FT) employment, part-time (PT) employment, education, and out of the labor force; family states distinguish cohabitation (cohab) with/without child and non-cohabitation with/without child (legend at right).

Figure A5: Individual sequence index plots for the 4-cluster solution.

State distribution plots ($k = 4$) showing the relative frequency of employment states (top row) and family states (bottom row) within each cluster across age (x-axis). Stacked areas sum to 1 at each age, indicating the composition of states within a cluster at that age.

Table 1: Sample Descriptives by Cluster

		Table 2:								
		Cluster 1: FT w Child (N=8415)		Cluster 2: FT w/o Child (N=2328)		Cluster 3: UE w Child (N=6820)		Cluster 4: PT w Child (N=3243)		
		Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	
ADL (dichotomised)		0.2	0.4	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.1	0.4	
Self-rated Health (dichotomised)		0.4	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.5	
Depression (dichotomised)		0.3	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.4	
No. Childhood Conditions		1.4	0.9	1.4	1.0	1.4	0.9	1.3	0.9	
Self-rated Health (baseline)		3.9	1.1	3.9	1.0	3.8	1.0	3.9	1.0	
Ever missed school for 1mo		0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	
Ever confined to bed for 1mo		0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	
Ever hospitalised for 1mo		0.9	0.2	0.9	0.2	0.9	0.2	1.0	0.2	
No. of rooms at home (age 10)		3.9	1.9	3.8	1.9	4.0	2.0	3.7	1.7	
People in HH (age 10)		5.5	2.2	5.4	2.5	5.5	2.4	5.4	2.0	
Rooms per person (age 10)		0.8	0.4	0.8	0.4	0.8	0.4	0.8	0.4	
No. of Books (age 10)		2.3	1.3	2.2	1.2	2.2	1.2	2.1	1.2	
No. of home features (age 10)		2.6	1.8	2.5	1.8	2.5	1.8	2.4	1.8	
Math Achievement (age 10)		3.2	0.9	3.2	0.9	3.2	0.9	3.2	0.9	
Language Achievement (age 10)		3.4	0.8	3.4	0.8	3.4	0.9	3.4	0.9	
Education Years (baseline)		10.6	4.5	10.5	4.5	10.6	4.6	10.4	4.6	
Migrant		0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	0.9	0.2	
Mother attended HS (baseline)		0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.1	0.4	
Father attended HS (baseline)		0.3	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.3	0.4	
Years w Disease (dichotomised)		0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	
Age		18.0	0.0	18.0	0.0	18.0	0.0	18.0	0.0	
		N	Pct.	N	Pct.	N	Pct.	N	Pct.	
Welfare Regime										
		Corporatist	3984	47.3	1130	48.5	4153	60.9	1082	33.4
		Mediterranean	2509	29.8	751	32.3	1782	26.1	1415	43.6
		Scandinavian	1922	22.8	447	19.2	885	13.0	746	23.0

Notes: Cluster-stratified descriptives (mean and s.d.) for outcomes and baseline covariates across four trajectory clusters: FT with child (N=8,415), FT without child (N=2,328), UE with child (N=6,820), and PT with child (N=3,243). Outcomes are dichotomised measures of ADL, self-rated health, and depression. Covariates summarize childhood conditions and household resources (age 10), baseline education and parental schooling, migrant status, and baseline age. The bottom panel reports welfare-regime composition as counts and percentages. ADL, Activities of Daily Living; FT, full-time; PT, part-time; UE, unemployed; HS, high school; HH, household.

A2. Alternative Cluster Specifications

The main alternative cluster specification suggested by the silhouette analysis in A2 is a 7-cluster solution (shown in A6). While this specification would recover several trajectories that are not present in the final 4-cluster solution, such as combinations of full-time employment with childlessness and no cohabitation, or childbearing without cohabitation, it would also fragment the sample substantially. In particular, cluster sizes become small in the Mediterranean and Scandinavian subsamples, with some clusters containing fewer than 200 individuals, which limits statistical power and makes cross-regional comparisons unstable.

Figure A6: Alternative 7-cluster specification.

Employment (top row) and family (bottom row) profiles for the 7-cluster solution proposed by the silhouette analysis. Plots display relative frequencies of states across age within each cluster (stacked areas sum to 1 at each age).

We also examined specifications closer to the adopted 4-cluster solution, although these are not necessarily favored by A2: a 3-cluster solution (A7) and a 5-cluster solution (A8). The 3-cluster solution offers limited substantive differentiation in family trajectories, as all medoids are characterized by cohabitation with children, leaving no distinct “non-family” or “non-cohabiting” family-related trajectory. The 5-cluster solution introduces an additional family-treatment trajectory characterized by transitions into non-cohabitation with children. However, as in the 7-cluster specification, this additional cluster is small, particularly in the Mediterranean and Scandinavian samples, rendering estimates based on this group imprecise and reducing its analytical usefulness.

Figure A7: Alternative 7-cluster specification.

Figure A8: Alternative 7-cluster specification.

Appendix B. Causal Framework and Estimation

Focus: Identification assumptions and modeling strategy for g-computation

Includes: Causal framework, modeling of covariates and outcomes, and estimation methods.

B1. Causal Framework

To estimate the causal effects of work-family trajectories, we apply the g-formula¹⁻⁴, which enables estimation of potential outcomes under hypothetical interventions on longitudinal treatment paths while adjusting for time-varying confounding.

G-computation is well-suited for this study's extended time horizon (32 years). Marginal Structural Models (MSMs), for example, based on inverse probability of treatment weighting (IPTW) are often applied in social science research, but they can suffer from instability due to extreme weights and positivity violations in long follow-up settings⁵. In contrast, g-computation flexibly models the joint distribution of covariates and outcomes, allowing for credible simulation of counterfactual outcomes under complex treatment trajectories.

Formally, the g-formula expresses the expected potential outcome under a time-varying treatment sequence \vec{a} as:

$$\mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}}] = \int \mathbb{E}[Y \mid \vec{A} = \vec{a}, \vec{L} = \vec{l}] dP(\vec{l} \mid \vec{A} = \vec{a})$$

where: $\vec{A} = \{A_1, \dots, A_T\}$ is the treatment trajectory (employment, cohabitation, childbearing), $\vec{L} = \{L_1, \dots, L_T\}$ is the time-varying covariate history, Y is the outcome (Depression, ADLs, Self-rated Health).

B2. Causal Assumptions and Justification

Identification of causal effects via the g-formula rests on the following assumptions:

1. Sequential Ignorability:

$Y^{\vec{a}} \perp\!\!\!\perp A_t \mid \vec{A}_{t-1}, \vec{L}_t$ for all t . That is, conditional on treatment and covariate history, treatment assignment is independent of potential outcomes.

2. Consistency:

If an individual follows $\vec{A} = \vec{a}$, then their observed outcome equals the potential outcome: $Y = Y^{\vec{a}}$.

3. Positivity (conventional):

$P(\vec{A} = \vec{a} \mid \vec{L} = \vec{l}) > 0$ for all (\vec{a}, \vec{l}) in the support.

4. Positivity (relaxed):

Each individual has a non-zero probability of following each trajectory type, conditional on baseline covariates:

$$P(\vec{A} \in \mathcal{C}_k \mid L_0 = \ell_0) > 0 \quad \text{for all } k \in \{1, \dots, K\}, \ell_0 \in \text{support},$$

where \mathcal{C}_k denotes the set of sequences assigned to cluster k , identified via sequence and clustering analysis. Medoid sequences represent the intervention trajectories within each cluster.

Sequential Ignorability. We assume no unmeasured confounding of treatment trajectories and outcomes, conditional on rich baseline (e.g., education, childhood health conditions, parental characteristics) and time-varying covariates (health shocks).

Consistency. The consistency assumption requires that, for individuals whose observed treatment history matches trajectory \vec{a} , the observed outcome equals the potential outcome: $Y = Y^{\vec{a}}$. Because medoid trajectories are based on actually observed and internally coherent patterns, they represent well-defined and realistic treatment paths, enhancing the plausibility of the consistency assumption.

Positivity. Given the high dimensionality of yearly treatment sequences over 32 years, we adopt a relaxed positivity assumption at the level of trajectory types. Specifically, we assume that each individual has a non-zero probability of following each medoid-defined trajectory type, conditional on their baseline covariates. This relaxation is necessary for identifying causal effects under the g-formula, as exact sequence-level positivity is typically violated in high-dimensional longitudinal data.

Interpretive Boundaries. These assumptions are untestable. Accordingly, we interpret estimates as causal under the assumption of selection on observables—that is, conditional on the covariates included in the model, potential outcomes are independent of treatment. The plausibility of this assumption rests on the richness of the observed covariates and the capacity of the Super Learner estimator to flexibly capture nonlinearities and interactions. In addition, our approach allows adjusting for time-varying confounders.

B3. Causal Estimand: Average Treatment Effect (ATE)

The primary causal quantity of interest is the Average Treatment Effect (ATE) of following a given medoid trajectory versus following the natural course. Formally:

$$\text{ATE}_{\vec{a}} = \mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}}] - \mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}^N}]$$

where \vec{a} is a medoid trajectory used as the intervention, and \vec{a}^N is the natural trajectory an individual would have otherwise followed. Under the consistency assumption:

$$\mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}^N}] = \mathbb{E}[Y]$$

Thus, the ATE simplifies to:

$$\text{ATE}_{\vec{a}} = \mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}}] - \mathbb{E}[Y]$$

This formulation enables direct comparison between the expected counterfactual outcome under an intervention trajectory and the average observed outcome in the sample.

B4. Modeling Covariates and Outcomes

G-computation proceeds in the following steps:

1. Fit the outcome model Y given treatment trajectory features, time-varying covariate, and baseline covariates;
2. Fit the time-varying covariate model conditional on prior treatment trajectory features and baseline covariates;
3. Update time-varying covariate under each treatment trajectory $\vec{L}^{\vec{a}}$ using the time-varying covariate model.
4. Predict potential outcomes $Y^{\vec{a}}$ under each treatment trajectory \vec{a} using the outcome model and updated time-varying covariates.
5. Estimate average treatment effects of treatment trajectory by estimating $\mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}}] - \mathbb{E}[Y]$
6. Estimate uncertainty of ATE using Monte Carlo simulation.

Outcome Model Specification

The outcome model is specified as:

$$Y \sim f[g(\vec{A}_{t-1}), L_t, L_0]$$

where $g(\cdot)$ includes trajectory-level summary and $f(\cdot)$ is estimated via Super Learner using:

- Treatment trajectory features $[g(\vec{A}_{t-1})]$ summarize employment and family trajectories.

- For employment trajectories, these features include the total number of years spent in full-time work and part-time work, as well as the number of work status transitions over time. We also identified the age or time of first entry into a full-time job, the longest continuous spell in any work status, and the last observed work status (full-time, part-time, in education, or not working). In addition, we determined each individual’s dominant work status over the observation period—whether they spent most of their time working full-time, part-time, in education, or not working. We further calculated the entropy of their work statuses to capture instability or variation in their employment patterns.
- For family trajectories, these features include the number of years spent cohabiting and not cohabiting, as well as the number of years living with children and without children. We also measured the number of transitions in cohabitation status, the age or time of first cohabitation, and the longest continuous spell of cohabitation. At the end of the observation period, we recorded whether individuals were cohabiting or not and whether they were living with children. We also identified the dominant cohabitation and family arrangement across the life course, distinguishing whether individuals spent most of their time cohabiting or not cohabiting, and with or without children. Finally, we calculated the entropy of cohabitation statuses to reflect instability or variability in living arrangements.
- Time-varying covariate $[L_t]$: A binary indicator for any year in which the individual had at least one disease during the observation period.
- Baseline covariates $[L_0]$: include pre-age 18 characteristics.

Covariate Model Specification

Each time-varying covariate L_t representing experiencing any year of having disease until age 50, is modeled as:

$$L_t \sim f[g(\vec{A}_{t-1}), L_0]$$

where $g(\cdot)$ indicates treatment trajectory features and $f(\cdot)$ is estimated via Super Learner using:

- Treatment trajectory features $[g(\vec{A}_{t-1})]$ are included as the same with the outcome model.
- Baseline covariates $[L_0]$: include pre-age 18 characteristics.

B5. Estimation and Implementation

All models are estimated using the Super Learner ensemble method, which selects the optimal weighted combination of candidate algorithms based on cross-validated predictive performance.

For time-varying covariate and outcome models, the ensemble includes lasso regression, random forest, and gradient boosting. Lasso regression provides robustness under multi-collinearity, while the nonparametric learners accommodate high-dimensional treatment features without imposing restrictive functional forms. Super Learner adaptively weighs these learners to balance robustness and flexibility across the covariate space.

To predict potential outcomes for each intervention trajectory \vec{a} , outcomes are predicted under the scenario in which all individuals follow \vec{a} . To take into account time-varying confounding, time-varying covariate $L_t^{\vec{a}}$ are updated using the fitted covariate model, conditional on the treatment trajectory features and base-line covariate. The potential outcome $Y^{\vec{a}}$ is then computed, using the updated time-varying covariate and treatment trajectory based on medoids. This follows the standard iterative g-computation procedure.

The average treatment effect (ATE) is computed as:

$$\text{ATE}_{\vec{a}} = \mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}}] - \mathbb{E}[Y]$$

Confidence intervals are constructed using 1,000 nonparametric bootstrap resamples⁶.

By comparing potential outcomes under the scenario in which all individuals follow the same treatment trajectory \vec{a} with observed outcomes without intervention, this approach estimates effects of following typical life trajectories on later health outcomes identified in our data.

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Appendix C. Welfare Regimes: An in-depth look

Focus: Delineate inclusion and exclusion criteria for countries in our analytical sample, the reasons behind their categorization, and offer an in-depth analysis of the welfare characteristics of the countries included to enrich the theoretical discussion of our results.

Includes: Welfare state theoretical background, review of classical categorizations, and descriptive analyses of welfare provisions by countries included in our dataframe.

C1. Welfare typologies and classifications

The seminal work of Gøsta Esping-Andersen, *The Three Worlds of Welfare Capitalism*¹, played a central role in shaping how welfare regimes are compared. In his original delineation, he categorized a total of 18 countries into three distinct welfare typologies: Liberal (Australia, Canada, Ireland, New Zealand, United Kingdom, and USA), Conservative (Finland, France, Germany, Japan, Italy, and Switzerland), and Social Democratic (Austria, Belgium, Netherlands, Denmark, Norway, and Sweden). This categorization is cemented around the ideas of decommodification and social stratification, that is, the degree in which citizens can maintain a socially acceptable standard of living independent of market participation, and the ways welfare institutions reproduce or reduce social cleavages¹.

- **Liberal.** Low levels of decommodification: residual and income-capped provisions with barely universal elements. Benefits are typically flat-rate and targeted, encouraging reliance on markets and private insurance¹.
- **Conservative.** Medium decommodification concentrated on labor-market insiders via earnings-related social insurance financed by contributions, perpetuating occupational/status differences. Although the generosity of provisions may in some instances match that of Social Democratic systems, benefits are rarely universal¹.
- **Social Democratic.** High decommodification and universalism: tax-financed, encompassing benefits and services oriented to individuals. Stratification is actively compressed through universal coverage and generous replacement rates.¹

However, despite the scope and influence of this seminal piece, it also gathered extensive conceptual and methodological critiques²⁻⁴. These criticisms have fostered the proliferation of rival welfare typologies, each with different conceptual guidelines, classification criteria, and country samples⁵. The first, and probably most compelling, round of criticism was regarding his omission of several Southern European nations (Greece,

Portugal, and Spain). This oversight was particularly perplexing since these three countries were founding members of the OECD in 1961 and, by the time of publication of the research, had been members of the EU since the early to mid-1980s. Leibfried first suggested the existence of a “Latin rim”⁶, which included France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain. Leibfried was followed by several authors who all argued for the necessity to classify the Southern European countries in a cluster of their own⁷⁻⁹, although none of these new taxonomies continued to group France with the rest of Southern Europe.

The most prominent advocate for the creation of a Mediterranean Welfare System category has probably been Maurizio Ferrera. In his work *The “Southern Model” of Welfare in Social Europe*⁷, Ferrera describes why the Southern European countries of Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain constitute a coherent fourth regime family, whose configuration is poorly captured by the classic Esping-Andersen typology.

- **Hybrid decommodification profile.** Southern systems decommodify heavily for old age, but the social protection for the working-age population is far more scant. That mix produces a high/low split that doesn’t fit Esping-Andersen’s single decommodification scale, being too protective to be “Liberal” but not offering enough work-related protections to be Bismarckian.
- **Stratification by employment status.** Benefits and access are organized around occupational status and contribution records, creating sharp insider-outsider divides and gaps for irregular workers and new labour-market entrants. Esping-Andersen’s “conservative” family of status-preserving insurance doesn’t anticipate the degree of fragmentation, clientelism, and administrative particularism Ferrera documents for Southern Europe.
- **Familialism vs. service state.** Ferrera also emphasizes strong reliance on the family and comparatively weak social services/childcare. The degree of dependence on the family as a source of social protection is unmatched in any other typology. This institutionalizes a specific gender order, framing women primarily as caregivers in contrast to the liberal regime’s construction of women as workers⁹.
- **Late but universal health-care.** Southern regimes developed universal health coverage comparatively late, especially relative to Scandinavian countries. Universal health care is typically associated with Social Democratic regimes, making its emergence in these otherwise less generous systems analytically distinctive.

The introduction of the familial dimension makes Ferrera’s classification ideal for studying women’s employment-family trajectories. Additionally, Bamba’s comparative study of twelve welfare state models (six typologies and six taxonomies) concluded

that Ferrera’s categorization presented the highest explanatory power out of the classifications included in the study,⁵ trailed by other configurations that also include the Mediterranean distinction, such as Leibfried⁶ or Bonoli⁸. Ferrera proposes four “welfare families”: a Scandinavian/Nordic group (Denmark, Sweden, Norway, Finland), an Anglo-Saxon/Liberal group (United Kingdom, Ireland), a Continental/Corporatist group (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Netherlands and Switzerland), and a Southern/Mediterranean group (Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece)⁷.

C2. SHARE countries and selection criteria

SHARE’s sample is comprised of a total of 28 European countries and Israel. 12 of them were present since its inception (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Israel, Spain, Switzerland, and Sweden). For the first retrospective module (SHARELIFE, Wave 3), the pool of participants had extended to 15 with the addition of the Czech Republic, Ireland, and Poland. By the last retrospective module (Wave 7), Estonia, Hungary, Portugal, Slovenia, Luxembourg, Croatia, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Romania, and Slovakia joined¹⁰.

Our analytical sample was restricted to countries that met two key criteria. First, they must have participated in at least one retrospective module, since this data is necessary for deriving employment and family trajectories. Second, they needed to be classified in existing welfare typology studies, with a preference for those included in Ferrera’s original framework⁷. Most of the countries employed by Ferrera in his original depiction of “welfare families”⁷ are present in the sample, with the sole exceptions of Norway and the United Kingdom.

We considered the inclusion of additional countries not featured in Ferrera’s original framework but ultimately excluded them for the following reasons:

- **Czech Republic:** This country appears in only three studies within our review, and its classification is highly inconsistent. It is sometimes grouped with other post-2000 EU expansion states like Estonia, Latvia, and Hungary¹¹, but also placed alongside France and Spain¹² or categorized as a corporatist state¹³. Given this lack of consensus, it was excluded.
- **Poland, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, and Slovakia:** These countries have received little attention from the academic community, appearing in just two of the reviewed papers. Additionally, their placement is also inconsistent, with all of them grouped with the aforementioned post-2000s expansion countries with the Czech Republic¹¹ but then separated either as post-Soviet states, in the Mediterranean section, or as a corporatist state¹³. The concept of a distinct “post-Soviet”

welfare typology has been criticized as reductionist, arguing it reflects historical precedent more than contemporary political configurations and overlooks substantial within-group variation^{14,15}.

- **Slovenia:** This country was identified in a single paper as a post-Communist regime, providing an insufficient basis for consistent classification.
- **Croatia, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Malta, and Romania:** These countries were not classified in any of the welfare typology studies included in our literature review.^{1,16,17}
- **Ireland:** Although Ireland is included in Ferrera’s original typology and consistently classified as a Liberal regime throughout our literature review, it is the sole representative of its kind in the SHARE sample. Consequently, the sample size for a Liberal regime was too small to form a statistically viable category for our analysis.

The literature review focused deliberately on research exploring pre- or early-2000 welfare configurations to ensure that typologies reflect the institutional context relevant to the life courses of individuals in our sample.

C3. Welfare configurations: a descriptive analysis of their evolution up to the 21st century

A limitation of the welfare-regime literature for our purposes is that it largely analyzes mature welfare states, capturing institutional logics and expenditure profiles as they stood in the late 1980s and early 1990s. As a result, existing typologies may not fully reflect the institutional environments that shaped the life courses of older cohorts in our sample. This is because individuals in the SHARE study largely spent their adult lives, when the key employment and family transitions took place, during the 1960s, 70s, and 80s. To better contextualize the welfare context that shaped these trajectories, this section extends the analysis further into the past, tracing the trajectories of public social expenditure, coverage, and types of welfare provisions. To do so we employ data from the Social Policy Indicators (SPIN)¹⁸ database and the OECD. It is important to note that this is an exploratory analysis. The data availability for the mid-20th century is limited, especially for some specific countries like Spain or Portugal, which constrains comparability. Nevertheless, this longitudinal perspective allows us to ground our regime classifications in the historical context that the cohorts in our sample actually experienced.

C3.1. Welfare provisions: Healthcare and disability

Our results seem to corroborate the original theoretical framework of Esping-Andersen, confirming that the Scandinavian (Social Democratic) regimes in our sample are characterized by earlier and stronger investments in broad social protections. Regime means for health expenditure as a share of GDP (Figure 1) start higher for Scandinavian regimes, followed by Corporatist regimes, with Mediterranean states lagging behind at less than half the spending level of the other two families in the early period. Expenditure rises between the 70s and the start of the 90s for all the regimes, with Scandinavian regimes retaining the lead until the mid-1990s, when Corporatist averages converge and eventually exceed them. However, while Corporatist regimes might display comparable levels of expenditure to Scandinavian countries, these aggregate measures mask profound differences in the structure and distribution of these resources.

Figure 1: Health expenditure as a % of GDP by welfare regimes.

These differences in access to healthcare provisions are illustrated by the trajectories of universal healthcare coverage (Figure 2). The Scandinavian regimes achieved and sustained universal coverage as early as the mid-1960s. In contrast, Corporatist regimes, while starting with a substantial base of around 80% coverage, saw their progress stagnate, plateauing at approximately 90% for decades. Conversely, Mediterranean countries

begin with the lowest coverage (just above 50% in 1960) but expand rapidly, approaching universality by the mid-1980s. In other words, even when expenditure in Corporatist regimes converged with or surpassed Scandinavian levels, the core tenet of the Scandinavian model, universality, remained a key differentiator.

Figure 2: % of population covered by healthcare by welfare regimes.

These findings provide empirical support for Ferrera’s characterization of the Mediterranean welfare model as separate from the Corporatist family⁷. First, the trajectory of healthcare coverage affirms his claim of a distinct “healthcare universalism,” which clearly differentiates the rapid, comprehensive expansion in Southern Europe from the stagnant, incomplete coverage that long persisted in Corporatist regimes. Second, data on pension generosity are consistent with Ferrera’s notion of a “hybrid decommodification profile.” As shown in Figure 3, Mediterranean regimes exhibit the highest pension replacement rates—the percentage of a worker’s pre-retirement income replaced by pensions. This strong emphasis on old-age provision is not matched in other welfare domains such as family and child benefits (Figures 4 and 5) or public/subsidized housing (Figure 6).

However, while generous, the pensions in Mediterranean regimes remain limited in their scope (Figure 7), covering between 40 and 60% of the population. Universality is, again, the core tenet of the Scandinavian regimes, maintaining pension coverage for the whole population for every year of the time series. Corporatist regimes demonstrate

Regime means — Pension for average worker

Figure 3: Pension's replacement rates for the average worker.

intermediate coverage levels, with values ranging from 65 to 70% for the observed period. Scandinavian countries also exhibit the highest levels of coverage and benefit duration for both sickness (Figure 8, 9) and parental leave (Figure 10, 11).

Taken together, what characterizes the Scandinavian model is not only the generosity of the benefits but also both the universality of the provisions and the wide array of policies and areas they cover. Comparatively, Corporatist and Mediterranean provisions are highly fragmentary, focusing in employment-linked benefits for Corporatists and pensions plus health care for Mediterranean countries. These patterns are not new in the comparative welfare literature, but our descriptive evidence shows that they are already in place by the 1960s and persist over subsequent decades. This reinforces our confidence that the welfare regime categories used in the main analysis capture the institutional configurations that actually structured women's employment and family trajectories over their adult lives.

Figure 4: Public spending on family-related assistance.

Figure 5: Public child benefits generosity.

Figure 6: Public spending on housing.

Figure 7: Pension coverage by regime.

Figure 8: Sickness cash benefits coverage by regime.

Figure 9: Sickness benefits extension by regime.

Figure 10: Parental leave benefits by regime.

Figure 11: Parental leave extension by regime.

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Appendix D. Treatment Effects Breakdown

Focus: Average treatment effect and its heterogeneity in various subgroups

Includes: Average treatment effect, treatment effect heterogeneity by cluster type, treatment effect heterogeneity by propensity score.

D1. Average Treatment Effect (ATE) by Welfare Regime

As appendix B3 shows, we estimate the **average treatment effect (ATE)** for each medoid trajectory, defined as

$$\text{ATE}_{\vec{a}} = \mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}}] - \mathbb{E}[Y],$$

where $\mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}}]$ denotes the expected potential outcome under an intervention trajectory \vec{a} , and $\mathbb{E}[Y]$ represents the averaged observed outcome in the sample. Table 1 presents the estimated ATEs for all medoids across the three welfare regimes.

To facilitate cross-regime comparisons and to standardize the magnitude of effects, we additionally compute **risk ratios** as a relative measure of treatment impact:

$$\text{Risk Ratio}_{\vec{a}} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}}]}{\mathbb{E}[Y]}.$$

The risk ratio expresses the expected outcome under treatment \vec{a} relative to the baseline expectation $\mathbb{E}[Y]$, providing a scale-invariant indicator of treatment magnitude. Summary estimates of the risk ratios are reported in Table 2.

Table 1: Raw ATE Summary by Regime and Medoid

Cluster	ADL 65–75	Depression 65–75	Self-rated Health 65–75
Corporatist			
Medoid 1: FT w Child	-0.044 [-0.057, -0.032]	-0.055 [-0.068, -0.042]	-0.084 [-0.097, -0.071]
Medoid 2: FT w/o Child	-0.048 [-0.058, -0.038]	-0.063 [-0.077, -0.050]	-0.093 [-0.106, -0.080]
Medoid 3: UE w Child	-0.021 [-0.032, -0.010]	-0.018 [-0.031, -0.005]	-0.047 [-0.060, -0.034]
Medoid 4: PT w Child	-0.017 [-0.028, -0.007]	-0.030 [-0.043, -0.017]	-0.031 [-0.044, -0.018]
Mediterranean			
Medoid 1: FT w Child	-0.048 [-0.058, -0.038]	-0.064 [-0.077, -0.051]	-0.084 [-0.097, -0.071]
Medoid 2: FT w/o Child	0.004 [-0.006, 0.014]	0.016 [0.002, 0.029]	0.009 [-0.004, 0.022]
Medoid 3: UE w Child	-0.030 [-0.040, -0.020]	-0.039 [-0.052, -0.025]	-0.047 [-0.060, -0.034]
Medoid 4: PT w Child	-0.010 [-0.020, 0.001]	-0.008 [-0.021, 0.005]	-0.011 [-0.024, 0.002]
Scandinavian			
Medoid 1 FT w Child	-0.029 [-0.040, -0.019]	-0.016 [-0.029, -0.003]	-0.062 [-0.073, -0.051]
Medoid 2 FT w/o Child	-0.006 [-0.016, 0.005]	-0.045 [-0.058, -0.032]	-0.067 [-0.079, -0.054]
Medoid 3 UE w Child	-0.030 [-0.041, -0.019]	-0.032 [-0.045, -0.019]	-0.047 [-0.059, -0.034]
Medoid 4 PT w Child	-0.003 [-0.013, 0.008]	-0.022 [-0.035, -0.010]	0.015 [0.001, 0.028]

Table 2: Risk Ratio Summary by Welfare Regimes

Medoid	ADL 65–75	Depression 65–75	Self-rated Health 65–75
Corporatist			
Medoid 1: FT w Child	0.713 [0.678, 0.751]	0.777 [0.746, 0.810]	0.716 [0.697, 0.735]
Medoid 2: FT w/o Child	0.661 [0.629, 0.696]	0.732 [0.702, 0.763]	0.671 [0.653, 0.689]
Medoid 3: UE w Child	0.779 [0.741, 0.820]	0.941 [0.904, 0.982]	0.848 [0.825, 0.871]
Medoid 4: PT w Child	0.811 [0.772, 0.853]	0.878 [0.843, 0.916]	0.863 [0.840, 0.887]
Mediterranean			
Medoid 1: FT w Child	0.700 [0.658, 0.746]	0.807 [0.776, 0.840]	0.846 [0.827, 0.867]
Medoid 2: FT w/o Child	1.025 [0.964, 1.093]	1.047 [1.007, 1.091]	1.017 [0.993, 1.041]
Medoid 3: UE w Child	0.815 [0.767, 0.868]	0.884 [0.850, 0.921]	0.915 [0.894, 0.937]
Medoid 4: PT w Child	0.950 [0.893, 1.012]	0.992 [0.954, 1.033]	0.989 [0.966, 1.013]
Scandinavian			
Medoid 1: FT w Child	0.626 [0.568, 0.693]	0.870 [0.803, 0.946]	0.860 [0.819, 0.906]
Medoid 2: FT w/o Child	0.808 [0.734, 0.896]	0.728 [0.672, 0.791]	0.770 [0.734, 0.811]
Medoid 3: UE w Child	0.825 [0.750, 0.915]	0.802 [0.739, 0.872]	0.855 [0.815, 0.900]
Medoid 4: PT w Child	0.947 [0.860, 1.049]	0.895 [0.826, 0.973]	1.043 [0.993, 1.100]

D2. Conditional Average Treatment Effect (CATE) by Cluster and Welfare Regime

To capture heterogeneity in treatment effects across both trajectory clusters and welfare regimes, we define the **Conditional Average Treatment Effect (CATE)** jointly over these two moderators. Let C denote the individual’s cluster membership, W denote the welfare regime, and $X = (C, W)$.

The CATE comparing an intervention trajectory \vec{a} to the natural trajectory \vec{a}^N , conditional on $(C = c, W = w)$, is defined as:

$$\text{CATE}_{\vec{a}}(c, w) = \mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}} \mid C = c, W = w] - \mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}^N} \mid C = c, W = w].$$

Under the consistency assumption, $Y^{\vec{a}^N} = Y$ whenever an individual follows their natural trajectory. Therefore:

$$\mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}^N} \mid C = c, W = w] = \mathbb{E}[Y \mid C = c, W = w].$$

Thus, the CATE simplifies to:

$$\text{CATE}_{\vec{a}}(c, w) = \mathbb{E}[Y^{\vec{a}} \mid C = c, W = w] - \mathbb{E}[Y \mid C = c, W = w].$$

This estimand quantifies the expected difference in outcomes between imposing the medoid trajectory \vec{a} and observing the natural trajectory, within each specific cluster–regime stratum. Table 4, 3, and 5 present the conditional average treatment effects (CATE) of different medoids at the cluster level and across different welfare regimes for activities of daily living (ADL), self-rated health, and depression, respectively.

D3. Heterogeneous Treatment Effect by Propensity Score

We estimate generalized propensity scores for the multi-level treatment using a multinomial logistic regression. This model predicts the probability of assignment to each medoid category k based on a set of time in-variant covariates X . The predicted probabilities $e_k(X) = \Pr(T = k \mid X)$ represents the probability that an individual would follow a given cluster-specific trajectory relative to all alternative clusters.

Figure A1 and Table 6 demonstrated the distribution summary of the the propensity of score of each medoid across three welfare regimes. Table 7. shows the coefficients of the propensity score covariates.

The generalized propensity score diagnostics indicate strong overlap across welfare regimes, which supports the comparability of the regime-specific effect estimates. A1

Table 3: Conditional Average Treatment Effects (CATE) under the Mediterranean Regime

Cluster	ADL 65–75	Self-rated Health 65–75	Depression 65–75
Medoid 1 : FT w Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.059 [-0.076, -0.042]	-0.094 [-0.114, -0.072]	-0.081 [-0.100, -0.061]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	-0.038 [-0.070, -0.009]	-0.069 [-0.110, -0.029]	-0.059 [-0.099, -0.019]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	-0.039 [-0.058, -0.019]	-0.083 [-0.107, -0.057]	-0.031 [-0.055, -0.008]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.045 [-0.066, -0.025]	-0.077 [-0.105, -0.049]	-0.078 [-0.105, -0.050]
Medoid 2: FT w/o Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.006 [-0.023, 0.011]	-0.001 [-0.021, 0.020]	0.000 [-0.020, 0.020]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	0.014 [-0.017, 0.044]	0.025 [-0.015, 0.065]	0.021 [-0.019, 0.061]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	0.013 [-0.007, 0.032]	0.011 [-0.013, 0.038]	0.048 [0.024, 0.071]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	0.006 [-0.015, 0.026]	0.017 [-0.011, 0.045]	0.001 [-0.026, 0.030]
Medoid 3: UE w Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.040 [-0.057, -0.023]	-0.056 [-0.076, -0.035]	-0.055 [-0.074, -0.035]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	-0.020 [-0.051, 0.010]	-0.031 [-0.072, 0.008]	-0.033 [-0.073, 0.007]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	-0.020 [-0.040, -0.001]	-0.045 [-0.070, -0.019]	-0.006 [-0.029, 0.018]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.027 [-0.047, -0.007]	-0.039 [-0.067, -0.011]	-0.052 [-0.080, -0.024]
Medoid 4: PT w Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.018 [-0.035, -0.001]	-0.016 [-0.036, 0.005]	-0.018 [-0.038, 0.001]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	0.002 [-0.029, 0.031]	0.009 [-0.031, 0.049]	0.003 [-0.037, 0.042]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	0.001 [-0.019, 0.020]	-0.004 [-0.029, 0.022]	0.030 [0.006, 0.053]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.006 [-0.026, 0.014]	0.002 [-0.026, 0.030]	-0.017 [-0.044, 0.011]

Table 4: Conditional Average Treatment Effects (CATE) under the Corporatist Regime

Cluster	ADL 65–75	Self-rated Health 65–75	Depression 65–75
Medoid 1: FT w Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.044 [-0.057, -0.032]	-0.104 [-0.122, -0.087]	-0.056 [-0.071, -0.039]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	-0.043 [-0.069, -0.017]	-0.108 [-0.141, -0.077]	-0.050 [-0.080, -0.021]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	-0.050 [-0.064, -0.037]	-0.121 [-0.138, -0.104]	-0.042 [-0.057, -0.028]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.043 [-0.069, -0.018]	-0.138 [-0.170, -0.107]	-0.074 [-0.105, -0.045]
Medoid 2: FT w/o Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.053 [-0.066, -0.040]	-0.123 [-0.140, -0.105]	-0.066 [-0.082, -0.050]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	-0.051 [-0.077, -0.025]	-0.126 [-0.159, -0.095]	-0.060 [-0.090, -0.031]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	-0.059 [-0.072, -0.046]	-0.140 [-0.157, -0.122]	-0.053 [-0.067, -0.039]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.052 [-0.077, -0.026]	-0.157 [-0.189, -0.125]	-0.085 [-0.115, -0.055]
Medoid 3: UE w Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.033 [-0.047, -0.021]	-0.051 [-0.068, -0.033]	-0.018 [-0.033, -0.001]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	-0.032 [-0.058, -0.006]	-0.054 [-0.088, -0.023]	-0.012 [-0.043, 0.017]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	-0.040 [-0.053, -0.026]	-0.068 [-0.085, -0.050]	-0.004 [-0.019, 0.010]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.032 [-0.058, -0.007]	-0.085 [-0.117, -0.053]	-0.035 [-0.066, -0.006]
Medoid 4: PT w Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.028 [-0.041, -0.016]	-0.045 [-0.063, -0.027]	-0.032 [-0.047, -0.016]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	-0.027 [-0.053, -0.001]	-0.048 [-0.082, -0.017]	-0.026 [-0.057, 0.002]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	-0.035 [-0.048, -0.021]	-0.061 [-0.079, -0.044]	-0.019 [-0.033, -0.005]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.027 [-0.053, -0.002]	-0.078 [-0.110, -0.047]	-0.050 [-0.081, -0.021]

Table 5: Conditional Average Treatment Effects (CATE) under the Scandinavian Regime

Cluster	ADL 65–75	Self-rated Health 65–75	Depression 65–75
Medoid 1: FT w Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.049 [-0.068, -0.033]	-0.051 [-0.073, -0.030]	-0.023 [-0.042, -0.003]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	-0.047 [-0.081, -0.009]	-0.070 [-0.116, -0.021]	-0.024 [-0.064, 0.013]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	-0.034 [-0.060, -0.012]	-0.017 [-0.051, 0.018]	-0.019 [-0.048, 0.008]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.044 [-0.072, -0.019]	-0.037 [-0.075, 0.000]	-0.018 [-0.052, 0.012]
Medoid 2: FT w/o Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.027 [-0.046, -0.011]	-0.078 [-0.101, -0.058]	-0.046 [-0.065, -0.026]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	-0.026 [-0.059, 0.011]	-0.098 [-0.145, -0.049]	-0.049 [-0.089, -0.011]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	-0.013 [-0.038, 0.010]	-0.043 [-0.078, -0.009]	-0.040 [-0.070, -0.014]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.022 [-0.050, 0.003]	-0.064 [-0.102, -0.027]	-0.041 [-0.074, -0.011]
Medoid 3: UE w Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	-0.025 [-0.044, -0.009]	-0.052 [-0.074, -0.031]	-0.034 [-0.053, -0.014]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	-0.024 [-0.057, 0.014]	-0.072 [-0.119, -0.022]	-0.036 [-0.076, 0.001]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	-0.011 [-0.036, 0.012]	-0.019 [-0.053, 0.016]	-0.029 [-0.059, -0.002]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.020 [-0.048, 0.005]	-0.038 [-0.075, -0.001]	-0.029 [-0.062, 0.001]
Medoid 4: PT w Child			
Cluster 1: FT w Child	0.004 [-0.021, 0.026]	0.007 [-0.016, 0.027]	-0.019 [-0.038, 0.001]
Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	-0.009 [-0.042, 0.029]	-0.014 [-0.060, 0.035]	-0.021 [-0.060, 0.017]
Cluster 3: UE w Child	0.004 [-0.021, 0.026]	0.037 [0.003, 0.072]	-0.014 [-0.044, 0.013]
Cluster 4: PT w Child	-0.006 [-0.033, 0.019]	0.018 [-0.018, 0.056]	-0.014 [-0.048, 0.016]

Figure A1: Boxplot for Propensity Score across Welfare Regime

shows broadly similar boxplots for each medoid’s propensity score across the Mediterranean, Scandinavian, and Corporatist samples, and 6 confirms that the central tendency and dispersion are closely aligned across regimes (e.g., “FT w Child” centers around 0.40 in all three regimes, and “UE w Child” around 0.31–0.34). This similarity suggests that the regime-specific samples occupy comparable regions of covariate space with respect to treatment assignment, reducing the extent to which cross-regime comparisons rely on extrapolation from non-overlapping subpopulations (i.e., mitigating practical violations of common support/positivity).

Table 6: Summary Statistics of Propensity Scores by Welfare Regime

Propensity Score of Medoid #	Central Tendency			Variability			
	Mean	SD	Median	Q25	Q75	Min	Max
Mediterranean (n = 6457)							
PS_1: FT w Child	0.400	0.028	0.398	0.381	0.416	0.243	0.708
PS_2: FT w/o Child	0.116	0.009	0.116	0.110	0.122	0.048	0.148
PS_3: UE w Child	0.314	0.033	0.310	0.292	0.331	0.140	0.672
PS_4: PT w Child	0.171	0.020	0.174	0.161	0.184	0.037	0.221
Scandinavian (n = 4000)							
PS_1: FT w Child	0.416	0.033	0.415	0.392	0.439	0.125	0.648
PS_2: FT w/o Child	0.110	0.010	0.110	0.104	0.117	0.018	0.150
PS_3: UE w Child	0.318	0.046	0.316	0.285	0.348	0.193	0.850
PS_4: PT w Child	0.156	0.026	0.159	0.136	0.177	0.007	0.221
Corporatist (n = 10349)							
PS_1: FT w Child	0.403	0.032	0.402	0.382	0.424	0.197	0.627
PS_2: FT w/o Child	0.110	0.010	0.111	0.104	0.117	0.033	0.146
PS_3: UE w Child	0.340	0.044	0.337	0.309	0.369	0.179	0.756
PS_4: PT w Child	0.146	0.026	0.148	0.128	0.166	0.013	0.214

Table 7: Propensity Score Model Results by Regime and Cluster

Variable	Corporatist		Mediterranean		Scandinavian				
	Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	Cluster 3: UE w Child	Cluster 4: PT w Child	Cluster 2: FT w/o Child	Cluster 3: UE w Child	Cluster 4: PT w Child			
(Intercept)	-7.205 (0.000)***	-13.502 (0.000)***	16.552 (0.000)***	0.319 (0.000)***	4.920 (0.000)***	-6.782 (0.000)***	-22.978 (0.000)***	-34.325 (0.000)***	-6.268 (0.000)***
	-0.020 (0.595)	0.015 (0.548)	0.019 (0.597)	-0.037 (0.475)	-0.033 (0.396)	-0.037 (0.376)	0.066 (0.278)	-0.073 (0.152)	-0.041 (0.440)
Education Years (baseline)	0.003 (0.713)	-0.023 (0.000)***	0.010 (0.247)	0.017 (0.134)	0.029 (0.000)***	0.025 (0.004)**	0.020 (0.228)	0.072 (0.000)***	0.024 (0.089)
Ever confined to bed for 1 mo	0.069 (0.038)*	0.117 (0.000)***	0.155 (0.000)***	-0.025 (0.000)***	-0.205 (0.000)***	0.058 (0.192)	-0.246 (0.000)***	-0.682 (0.000)***	-0.384 (0.000)***
Ever hospitalised for 1mo	-0.270 (0.000)***	-0.246 (0.000)***	0.162 (0.000)***	0.264 (0.000)***	0.019 (0.207)	-0.373 (0.000)***	0.303 (0.000)***	0.012 (0.781)	0.132 (0.001)**
Ever missed school for 1mo	-0.000 (0.997)	0.102 (0.001)***	-0.074 (0.030)*	0.319 (0.000)***	0.409 (0.000)***	-0.101 (0.019)*	0.319 (0.000)***	0.504 (0.000)***	0.236 (0.001)***
Father attended HS (baseline)	0.022 (0.590)	0.127 (0.003)**	-0.150 (0.000)***	0.289 (0.000)***	-0.265 (0.000)***	0.006 (0.934)	0.232 (0.021)*	0.629 (0.000)***	0.293 (0.002)**
Language Achievement (age 10)	0.016 (0.721)	0.077 (0.009)**	0.014 (0.753)	-0.049 (0.451)	-0.048 (0.319)	-0.083 (0.109)	-0.140 (0.035)*	-0.047 (0.367)	-0.034 (0.539)
Math Achievement (age 10)	-0.072 (0.097)	-0.047 (0.100)	-0.041 (0.354)	-0.035 (0.554)	0.007 (0.867)	0.046 (0.326)	0.027 (0.684)	-0.016 (0.757)	0.057 (0.288)
Migrant	0.009 (0.549)	0.097 (0.100)	0.022 (0.104)	0.210 (0.000)***	-0.313 (0.000)***	-0.011 (0.000)***	0.029 (0.001)***	0.461 (0.000)***	0.110 (0.000)***
Mother attended HS (baseline)	-0.012 (0.662)	0.102 (0.037)*	-0.151 (0.000)***	-0.329 (0.000)***	-0.354 (0.000)***	-0.066 (0.073)	0.100 (0.248)	0.143 (0.124)	0.044 (0.658)
No. of Books (age 10)	-0.055 (0.095)	-0.034 (0.126)	-0.022 (0.507)	-0.065 (0.254)	0.084 (0.038)*	0.020 (0.657)	-0.094 (0.072)	-0.189 (0.000)***	-0.135 (0.002)**
No. of home features (age 10)	0.015 (0.519)	-0.038 (0.014)*	0.024 (0.310)	-0.023 (0.455)	-0.021 (0.352)	-0.058 (0.018)*	-0.076 (0.018)*	-0.144 (0.000)***	-0.015 (0.589)
No. of rooms at home (age 10)	-0.020 (0.308)	-0.032 (0.009)**	-0.018 (0.333)	-0.019 (0.571)	0.142 (0.000)***	0.084 (0.001)**	0.011 (0.711)	0.083 (0.000)***	0.034 (0.151)
People in HH (age 10)	-0.012 (0.443)	-0.004 (0.683)	0.023 (0.116)	-0.043 (0.029)*	-0.060 (0.000)***	-0.092 (0.000)***	0.024 (0.394)	0.017 (0.435)	-0.014 (0.579)
Rooms per person (age 10)	-0.090 (0.000)***	0.127 (0.000)***	0.026 (0.000)***	-0.040 (0.000)***	-0.524 (0.000)***	-0.463 (0.000)***	0.085 (0.000)***	-0.002 (0.756)	0.068 (0.000)***
Self-rated Health (dichotomised)	0.070 (0.043)*	0.029 (0.216)	-0.065 (0.060)	0.033 (0.452)	0.036 (0.263)	0.103 (0.003)**	-0.023 (0.676)	-0.037 (0.400)	-0.019 (0.676)

Notes. Entries are coefficients with p-values in parentheses. Significance: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Appendix E. Missing Value and Imputation Strategy

Focus: Missing Values and the imputation Strategy

Includes: baseline variables imputation, missing values, missing value imputation strategy.

To address missing values in the baseline (time-invariant) covariates, we used a structured imputation procedure with the `mice`¹ package in R. Baseline variables were defined as conceptually stable characteristics that should remain constant across survey waves. We applied predictive mean matching (PMM) with a single imputed dataset ($m = 1$). PMM replaces missing values with observed values from respondents with similar predicted scores, ensuring realistic distributions and avoiding model-based extrapolation. This approach produces a consistent set of baseline covariates that respects their time-invariant nature, resolves cross-wave inconsistencies, and preserves empirically plausible values while minimizing parametric assumptions.

Figure A1: Proportion of missing value of baseline variables

References

- [1] Buuren SV, Groothuis-Oudshoorn K. **mice** : Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations in *R*. Journal of Statistical Software. 2011;45(3). Available from: <http://www.jstatsoft.org/v45/i03/>.